

A.

B.

Figure 2. 2D electrophoresis profile of Coomassie stained crude extract of *S. cervi* exposed to EOS. A. Control; B. Treated. The first dimension was performed on pH 3-10 IPG strips followed the second on 10% SDS-PAGE.